

Fiber Fragmentation Behavior Analysis in Single Carbon Fiber Epoxy Composites

Shinji Ogihara*, Katsuya Maruyama** and Yasuo Kogo***

*Department of Mechanical Engineering, Tokyo University of Science, 2641 Yamasaki, Noda, Chiba 278-8510, Japan

** Graduate Student, Tokyo University of Science

*** Department of Materials Science and Technology, Tokyo University of Science

SUMMARY: Fragmentation behavior in single carbon fiber epoxy composites is investigated experimentally and analytically. Strength distribution of the carbon fibers is also measured. Fiber fragment process is observed during the tensile loading. The effect of the loading rate on the fiber fragmentation behavior is discussed. A Monte Carlo simulation technique is used to describe the fiber fragment behavior in the fragmentation tests. Both cases where elastic stress transfer between the fiber and matrix and constant shear stress presents are considered. It is found that the fiber fragmentation behavior is well predicted using measured fiber strength data and assumed shear stress between fiber and matrix.

KEYWORDS: fragmentation test, carbon/epoxy, interface, fiber strength distribution, interfacial shear stress, Monte Carlo simulation

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that effect of the properties of the fiber/matrix interface on the mechanical properties of fiber reinforced composites is very significant. In order to develop high performance composite materials, it is very important to understand the relation between interface properties and composite macroscale properties. A fragmentation test is often used as an evaluation method of the fiber/matrix interface properties of fiber reinforced composite materials [1-6]. In the fragmentation test, single fiber composites are loaded in tension in the fiber direction. During the test, multiple fiber fractures occur and the fiber breaks saturate at high composite strain levels. The interfacial shear stress is evaluated from the average fiber fragment length when the fiber breaks saturate. However, the fragmentation test has two major problems. One of them is that the strain at which the interfacial shear stress is evaluated is much higher than the fracture strain of the unidirectional composite material in the fiber direction. The other is that only the average fiber strength is used to evaluate the interfacial shear stress, ignoring the statistical fiber strength distribution.

Curtin presented an analysis which can predict the relationship between the fiber break density and the composite strain during the fragmentation test, considering the statistical fiber strength distribution [2]. The interfacial shear stress is assumed to be constant. The technique can be used as a method to determine the fiber strength distribution and the fiber/matrix interfacial shear stress [3-4].

In the present study, the fiber fragmentation behavior during the fragmentation test is evaluated. The effect of loading rate (strain rate) is investigated experimentally. A Monte Carlo simulation technique is also used to describe the relation between the fiber break density and the composite strain. Two cases are considered. One is that the elastic stress transfer between the fiber and the matrix presents. Another is that the fiber/matrix interfacial shear stress is constant. The effect of strain rate on the interfacial shear stress is discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A carbon fibers used in the present study is T700S. Mechanical properties of the carbon fiber are shown in Table 1. Tensile tests are performed on the carbon fibers to evaluate the fiber strength distribution. The gage length is 25mm, and an Instron type tensile testing machine is used with a crosshead speed of 1mm/min.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of T700S carbon fiber

Young's modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (GPa)	Ultimate strain (%)	Diameter (μm)
230	4.9	2.1	6.9

For fragmentation tests, single carbon fiber composite specimens are fabricated. Bisphenol-A type epoxy resin (Epikote828; Japan Epoxy Resin Inc.) and triethylenetetramine (TETA) as hardener are used in 100:11 weight ratios as the matrix resin. The resin is cured at 50°C for 60 min and post cured at 100°C for 80 min.

A single carbon fiber is extracted randomly from the roving and mounted on a Teflon mold. The resin mixed with hardener is poured into the mold to obtain a single fiber reinforced epoxy composites specimen. The specimen is 72 mm long, 16 mm wide and 1 mm thick. Figure 1 shows the specimen configuration used in the fragmentation test. A strain gage whose gage length is 2mm is put on a specimen as shown in Fig.1.

Fragmentation tests are performed using a loading device put on the stage of an optical microscope (Figure 2). The number of fiber breaks is measured at every 0.1 % composite strain. The fiber break density is defined as the number of the fiber breaks per unit specimen length. In addition, the damage around fiber break is also observed. To discuss the difference in fragmentation behavior due to the difference in strain rate, three crosshead speeds are used, that is, 0.1 mm/min., 1.0 mm/min. and 10. 0mm/min., which correspond to strain rate of 8.3×10^{-5} (/s), 8.3×10^{-4} (/s) and 8.3×10^{-3} (/s), respectively.

Figure 1. Specimen configuration for fragmentation test.

Figure 2. Schematic of the system used for in-situ observation of the fragmentation process in single fiber composites

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fiber strength distribution obtained by the tensile test on the carbon fibers is assumed to be Weibull distribution which is expressed by

$$P = 1 - \exp\left\{-\frac{L}{L_0}\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^\rho\right\} \quad (1)$$

where P is failure probability of a fiber with length is L at stress σ . ρ is the shape parameter and σ_0 is the scale parameter. We set L_0 the gage length, that is, 25mm in the present study. The Weibull parameters (shape parameter ρ , and scale parameter σ_0) can be determined by fitting the following equation to the experimental data.

$$\ln\{-\ln(1-P)\} = \rho \ln \sigma - \rho \ln \sigma_0 + \ln \frac{L}{L_0} \quad (2)$$

Figure 3 shows the Weibull plot for T700S carbon fibers. The Weibull plot is fitted by a straight line by using the least square method and the Weibull parameters are obtained. The Weibull parameters are listed in Table 2. The parameters are used in the Monte Carlo simulation of the fiber fragmentation behavior.

Figure 3. Weibull plot of fiber strength distribution for T700S carbon fibers.

Table 2. Weibull parameters, ρ and σ_0 for T700S carbon fiber strength distribution

ρ	5.63
σ_0 [MPa]	5.56

Figure 4 show the typical experimental results of the fiber break density in the fragmentation test as a function of the applied composite strain. It is seen that as the strain rate increases the saturate fiber break density increases.

A Monte Carlo technique is used to predict fiber break density as a function of applied composite strain. The fibers are divided into elements in which only one fracture occurs. Generated random fiber strengths are assigned to the elements. In the present study, two cases are considered for the stress transfer between the fiber and the matrix. In case 1, it is assumed that the elastic stress transfer between the fiber and matrix presents. The stress transfer mechanics based on the approximate elasticity solution developed by McCartney [7] is used. In case 2, it is assumed that the fiber/matrix interfacial shear stress is constant.

In Fig.4 the simulation results by case 1 are also shown. Materials properties used in the simulation are listed in Table 3. It is seen that the simulation results overestimates the fiber break density at higher strain levels. This may be because the elastic solution overestimates the shear stress between the fiber and matrix especially at higher strain levels.

Table 3 Materials properties used in the simulation (case 1: elastic stress transfer between the fiber and matrix)

Fiber Axial Young's Modulus (GPa)	230
Fiber Transverse Young's Modulus (GPa)	13.8
Fiber Axial Shear Modulus (GPa)	18.0
Fiber Axial Poisson's Ratio	0.20
Fiber Transverse Poisson's Ratio	0.35
Fiber Axial Coefficient of Thermal Expansion ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	0.26×10^{-6}
Fiber Transverse Coefficient of Thermal Expansion ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	26.0×10^{-6}
Matrix Young's Modulus (GPa)	2.67
Matrix Poisson's Ratio	0.35
Matrix Coefficient of Thermal Expansion ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	60.0×10^{-6}
Element Length (mm)	0.45
Difference between Testing and Curing Temperatures ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	-80.0

Figure 4. Typical experimental results of the relation between the fiber break density as a function of applied strain during the fragmentation test. The Monte Carlo simulation results are also shown for the case where the elastic stress transfer between the fiber and the matrix is present.

Figure 5 shows comparison between the simulation and experimental results for the relation between the fiber break density and the applied composite strain by case 2. In the simulation, we choose the value of the constant interfacial shear stress to fit the experimental data. The chosen values for the interfacial shear stress are shown in Table 4. It is found that the interfacial shear stress is higher for the higher strain rate.

(a) Strain rate = 8.3×10^{-5} (/s)

(b) Strain rate = 8.3×10^{-4} (/s)

Figure 5. Comparison between the Monte Carlo simulation and experimental results for the relation between the fiber break density and the applied strain for (a) Strain rate = 8.3×10^{-5} (/s) , (b) Strain rate = 8.3×10^{-4} (/s), and (c) Strain rate = 8.3×10^{-3} (/s)

Table 4 Fiber/matrix interfacial shear stress (assumed values in the simulation)

Strain rate (/s)	8.3×10^{-5}	8.3×10^{-4}	8.3×10^{-3}
Interfacial Shear Stress (MPa)	35	45	55

CONCLUSIONS

Fragmentation behavior in single carbon fiber epoxy composites is investigated experimentally and analytically. A Monte Carlo simulation technique is used to predict the relation between the fiber break density and the applied composite strain. The measured strength distribution of the carbon fibers is used in the simulation. The effect of the loading rate on the fiber fragmentation behavior is discussed. Both cases where elastic stress transfer between the fiber and matrix and constant shear stress presents are considered. It is found that the fiber fragmentation behavior is well predicted using measured fiber strength data and assumed shear stress between fiber and matrix.

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